

Intercube Communication for the iPSC/860

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Abstract

In this paper, new functions that enable efficient intercube communication on the Intel iPSC/860 are introduced. Communication between multiple cubes (power-of-two number of processor nodes) within the Intel iPSC/860 is a desirable feature to facilitate the implementation of interdisciplinary problems such as the grand challenge problems of the High Performance Computing and Communications Project (HPCCP). Intercube communication allows programs for each discipline to be developed independently on the hypercube and then integrated at the interface boundaries using intercube communication.

1 Introduction

In this paper, new functions that enable efficient intercube communication on the Intel iPSC/860 are introduced. Communication between multiple cubes (power-of-two number of processor nodes) within the Intel iPSC/860 is a desirable feature to facilitate the implementation of interdisciplinary problems such as the grand challenge problems of the High Performance Computing and Communications Project (HPCCP). Intercube communication allows programs for each discipline to be developed independently on the hypercube and then integrated at the interface boundaries using intercube communication. Intercube communication is also useful within a single discipline where the physical domain is broken into several zones (computational domains) to facilitate grid generation or to accommodate bodies in relative motion. For good load balance, in both interdisciplinary and multizone problems, the number of computational nodes assigned to a computational domain should match the workload associated with that domain.

Currently, there are three ways to implement intercube communication on the Intel iPSC/860: individual cubes can communicate through the service re-

source module (SRM), via a shared file on the concurrent file system (CFS), or allocate a cube large enough to hold all desired subcubes and manage subcube allocation and communication from within the user program. All three methods have problems. Communicating through the SRM is slow because the SRM must receive the message, attach to the destination cube and then forward the message. Communicating through the CFS is not much better, since cubes must coordinate access to shared files. Having the user allocate and partition a single large cube places the burden of partitioning on the user and makes it more difficult to do independent development of domain specific code. Also, a single large cube partitioned into subcubes may lead to poor load balance if the code for a domain is designed to work with a power-of-2 number of processor nodes and the sum over all domains is not a power-of-2 number of nodes.

The intercube communication described in this paper differs from previous work [4] in that it implements intercube communication on a specific platform using existing hardware and routing algorithm. The intercube communication is fast and efficient. Fast because it sends messages using the hypercube wires without going to the SRM or CFS. Efficient because there is little additional overhead associated with sending an intercube message compared to a regular message. Overhead is primarily due to the verification and validation of the destination.

In addition to interdisciplinary and multizone programs, intercube communication is useful for functional partitioning of programs. For example, if one cube is generating a large amount of data, a second cube can be processing the data as it is generated in parallel.

In the remainder of the paper a discussion dealing with routing, allocation and contention is followed by the implementation of the intercube communication and an example demonstrating intercube communication. It is assumed that the reader is familiar with the Intel iPSC/860 system calls. For more information

Figure 1: e-cube routing of a message from node 0 to node 7.

about the iPSC/860 see [1] and [2].

2 Routing, Allocation and Contention

In this section, e-cube routing, cube allocation and sources of intercubes communication contention are described followed by a discussion of when intercubes communication may cause intracube communication contention within another cube.

2.1 e-cube Routing

The routing algorithm used on the Intel hypercubes is called e-cube routing. In e-cube routing, the source address and destination address are XORed and the resulting nonzero entries indicate which wires the message will traverse. Wires are traversed starting from the lowest order nonzero and proceed to the highest order nonzero. In practice, as the message is passed to each new node, the destination address is XORed with the local address and the message moved across the wire indicated by lowest order nonzero. When XORing with the local address, if the result is zero then the message has reached its destination. Figure 1 shows the path a message takes from node 0 to node 7 using e-cube routing.

2.2 Cube Allocation

When allocating a cube on an Intel hypercube, the physical address of logical node zero must be a multiple of the cube size. The operating system will not

Figure 2: Cubes of size 4 formed from (a) contiguous nodes and (b) noncontiguous nodes.

allocate a cube starting at a node whose physical address is not a multiple of the cube size.

Also, if a location is specified when a cube is requested, nodes with contiguous physical addresses will be assigned. If contiguous nodes cannot be assigned, the cube will not be allocated.

If a location is not specified, the operating system will allocate a cube if possible. However, the nodes are not guaranteed to be contiguous. The operating system tries to allocate contiguous nodes and then looks for other hypercubes if there are not enough contiguous nodes. Figure 2a shows a cube of size four formed from contiguous nodes whereas Figure 2b shows a cube of size four formed from noncontiguous nodes. Contiguous node allocation is the most common case [3].

2.3 Intercube Contention

Possible sources of contention for intercubes communication are the operating system downloading programs, users communicating with the SRM, and users communicating with the CFS. All of these sources exist and have existed within current systems and the author is not aware of users complaining about them.

One characteristic of all intercubes communication is that it occurs infrequently. Programs are downloaded once per cube. Programs are I/O bound if they communicate with the CFS too frequently. The SRM is a bottleneck if users communicate with it too often. Communicating interface boundary data in interdisciplinary or multizone programs also occurs infrequently.

2.4 Intracube Contention

During intercubes communication it is possible to interfere with intracube communication occurring within another cube. However, if all cubes are formed from contiguously allocated nodes with starting ad-

Figure 3: Intracube contention from intercube communication.

addresses that are a multiple of the cube size, intercube communication cannot interfere with intracube communication within another cube.

The potential for intercube communication to interfere with intracube communication within another cube is demonstrated in Figure 3. In Figure 3 there are two users, $user_1$ owns two cubes each of size one (node 0 and node 7) and $user_2$ owns one cube of size two (nodes 1 and 3). The cube owned by $user_2$ is not formed from contiguous nodes creating the possibility of contention. When $user_1$ sends a message between cubes from node 0 to node 7, the e-cube routing algorithm requires it to pass between node 1 and node 3 potentially interfering with the intracube communication of $user_2$.

Fortunately, when all cubes are allocated from contiguous nodes starting on physical node addresses that are a multiple of the cube size, intercube communication cannot interfere with the intracube communication within another cube. To see this, let the cube size be given by N and the cube dimension by $D = \log_2(N)$. Since the starting physical node address must be a multiple of the cube size, the low order D bits of the address are zero. The N contiguous physical addresses of a cube use those empty low order bits. When sending an intercube message, any bit differences between the source and destination in the low order D bits are eliminated by sending the message around inside the local cube¹. At this point, only high order bit differences are left.

Every cube has a natural partner formed from the

¹Recall that e-cube routing processes bit differences from low order to high order.

cube of the same size and starting address but with the $(D + 1)$ low order bit complemented². They are natural partners because they are the only cubes of size N in the proper locations to form a cube of size $2N$ satisfying the contiguous address and starting address constraints. If the $(D + 1)$ bit differs between the source and destination, the message will travel between the two cubes of size N . However, this link cannot be in use by either cube for intracube communication and so does not cause interference inside the other cube. By induction it can be shown that given contiguous nodes and starting addresses that are a multiple of the cube size, intercube communication cannot interfere with intracube communication within another cube.

3 Implementation

The major premise for the intercube communication implementation is that the number of cubes and size of cubes required is known and does not change. Static allocation of cubes is a valid model for any application that has multiple fixed sized computational domains that need to communicate.

To make intercube communication flexible and easy to support, the intercube communication mechanism is general and implemented using a small number of new routines. Having a general intercube communication mechanism allows applications to tailor intercube communication to individual needs. Given a small number of new routines, less support is required when the operating system or underlying hardware changes.

This implementation of intercube communication requires a host program and each cube participating in intercube communication to be *registered*. After all cubes have been registered and before any communication takes place, information about each cube and the nodes within each cube is downloaded to all participating nodes. Then to perform intercube communication, a (cube name, node number) pair is mapped into a system node address that is passed to the regular communication routines such as *csend*. This implies that forced message types [1] and pairwise exchange [5] will work with intercube communication. Currently, there is a system limit of 10 cubes that can be allocated³.

²A cube equal to the whole machine has no partner.

³Only nine cubes can be allocated if you have a CFS since the CFS requires a cube.

3.1 Data Structure

The data structure containing information on all cubes registered has the following fields:

- Local cube name
- Total number of cubes
- For each cube
 - Cubename
 - Number of nodes
 - Mapping function from logical node numbers to system node addresses

For the Intel iPSC/860, with 128 nodes, this data structure is less than 1 KB⁴ and is directly proportional to the total number of nodes allocated. Every node receives a copy of the data structure.

A hash function based on the cube name is used to index into the data structure. The hash function groups the cube name into blocks of four characters (treating a block as an unsigned integer), adds them together ignoring overflow and returns the sum modulo the table size. If the last group has less than four characters, the group is right justified and then added.

If a collision occurs (the table entry indicated by the hash function is not empty and not the desired entry), entries on both sides of the hash location are examined. If collisions occur again, a linear search is started at the hash location plus two. An empty slot is guaranteed for insertion because the table size matches the maximum number of cubes that can be allocated. When searching for an entry in the table, if an empty slot is encountered or the whole table has been searched without finding the desired entry, the cube name is invalid.

3.2 New Host Routines

Functional descriptions of the newly implemented host routines are given below. Interfaces exist to FORTRAN and C programs. Each cube must be given a unique cube name up to 15 characters in length.

initcubecomm()

Initcubecomm freezes the number of cubes that are participating in intercube communication, interrogates the operating system for the system node addresses, fills in the data structure and then downloads

⁴This could be compressed significantly at the cost of extra processing to calculate the system node addresses.

it to all participating nodes. It must be called before performing any communication.

setactivecube(cubename)

Setactivecube takes a cube name as an argument, verifies that the cube is owned by the user, registers the cube if it has not been registered and then does an **attach** and **setpid** for that cube. **Setactivecube** is called every time the the host communicates with a different cube. **Sethostpid** must be called before the first call to **setactivecube**.

sethostpid(pid)

Sethostpid records a single host process identifier that is used for all cubes. The **setpid** function is called by **setactivecube** after attaching to a cube. **Sethostpid** must be called once before the first call to **setactivecube**.

3.3 New Node Routines

Functional descriptions of the newly implemented node routines are given below. Interfaces exist to FORTRAN and C programs.

cmpname(cubename1, cubename2)

Cmpname is a logical function that takes two cube names as arguments and returns TRUE if the names match and FALSE if they don't match.

cubemap(cubename, node)

Cubemap takes a cube name and logical node number as input parameters and returns the system node address. The system node address can then be passed to either the **csend** or **isend** communication routines⁵. Before returning the system node address, **cubemap** verifies that the cube is owned by the user and checks that the node number is valid for that cube.

cubeseize(cubename)

Cubeseize returns the size of the specified cube.

initcubecomm()

Initcubecomm downloads the data structure containing information on all participating nodes. It must be called before performing any communication.

mycube()

Mycube returns the local cube name.

numcubes()

⁵Existing communication routines recognize system node addresses as well as logical node addresses so no new communication primitives are required.

Figure 4: Ring formed from two cubes of size four.

`Numcubes` returns the number of cubes willing to participate in intercube communication.

4 Example

As an example of intercube communication, the sample ring code provided by Intel is modified to send a message around a ring formed from two different cubes which are joined at logical node one of each cube. Figure 4 shows two cubes of size four linked together by logical node 1 in each cube to form a single ring. To start a message around the ring, `cube1` receives a message from the host describing the length of the message and the number of times it should go around the ring. After each lap `cube1` sends the lap count back to the host. When the message has gone around the required number of times `cube1` reports the elapsed time.

Changes made to the host and node programs are shown in appendices A and B respectively.

4.1 Results

To determine whether the `cubemap` function has significant overhead, the ring example is timed with two cubes of size eight and compared to the ring program using a single cube of size sixteen. It should be noted that `cubemap` can be called once and the destination system node address saved, amortizing the overhead across all laps. `Cubemap` is called every lap to see if it has significant overhead. There is no significant difference in time when sending a 32 byte message 20 times around the ring formed from two cubes, each of size eight, when compared to sending the same size message around a single cube of size sixteen⁶.

⁶This version of the ring program is not Gray coded.

Cube Size	Location	Binary
8	0	0000000
8	120	1111000

Table 1: Cube sizes and locations.

The starting addresses of the cubes, expressed in decimal and binary, are given in Table 1. The binary addresses demonstrate that intercube communication takes place since the addresses differ in all high order bits.

A closer examination of the overhead indicates the communication with the SRM is the determining factor in the elapsed time. Timing only the calls to `cubemap` in the node program reveal a cost of 37 microseconds per call. Of this, 18 microseconds is associated with searching for the cube entry and the rest with the FORTRAN to C interface. From C, a call to `cubemap` takes about 24 microseconds.

5 Summary

Efficient general intercube communication has been implemented using a small number of new functions. By keeping the number of functions small, any changes to the operating system or machine can be accommodated easily. By making the routines general, an application can tailor intercube communication to its needs.

The number and size of cubes involved in intercube communication is static. Cubes desiring intercube communication must register and receive a data structure containing information about all participating cubes before performing any communication. The static allocation model applies to any application that has multiple fixed sized computational domains or can be functionally partitioned.

The intercube communication routines work from an Iris workstation as remote host and are callable from either FORTRAN or C. The routines should work on an Intel iPSC/2 and it is anticipated that they will work on the Intel Delta machine at CalTech and possibly on the Intel Paragon machine.

Status

A fluid dynamics/thermal interdisciplinary code has been implemented by Sisira Weeratunga of NASA Ames using the intercube communication routines.

Currently, a fluid dynamics/structures code is being developed by Sisira Weeratunga and Eddy Pramono.

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References

- [1] *iPSC/2 and iPSC/860 Programmer's Reference Manual*, Intel Supercomputer Systems Division, Beaverton, Oregon, April 1991.
- [2] *iPSC/2 and iPSC/860 User's Guide*, Intel Supercomputer Systems Division, Beaverton, Oregon, June 1990.
- [3] Private communication with Paul Pierce of Intel Scientific Computers Division.
- [4] S. Padmanabhan and C. Baru, "Routing between Subcubes in a Hypercube", *Proceedings of the 6th Distributed Memory Computing Conference*, pp.295-298, April 1991.
- [5] S. Seidel, M. H. Lee, and S. Fotedar, "Concurrent Bidirectional Communication on the Intel iPSC/860 and iPSC/2", *Michigan Technological University Technical Report CS-TR 90-06*, November 1990.

Appendix A: FORTRAN Ring Example Host Code Modifications

```
parameter (NUMCUBES=2)
character*15 cube(NUMCUBES)
character*1 digit(0:9)
data digit/'0','1',..., '9'/
:
do i = 1, NUMCUBES
  cube(i) = "cube" // digit(i)
  call getcube(cube(i),...)
end do
call sethostpid(pid)
do i = 1, NUMCUBES
  call setactivecube(cube(i))
  call load('node',ALLNODES,0)
end do
call initcubecomm()
:
call setactivecube(cube(1))
call csend(INITTYPE,msgbuf,MSGSIZE,0,0)
:
call crecv(COUNTTYPE,msgbuf,CNTMSGSIZE)
:
do i = 1, NUMCUBES
  call setactivecube(cube(i))
  call killcube(ALLNODES,0)
  call relcube(cube(i))
end do
stop
end
```

Appendix B: FORTRAN Ring Example Node Code Modifications

```
parameter (NUMCUBES=2,INTERCUBE=50)
integer*4 cubemap
logical cmpname
character*15 cube(NUMCUBES)
character*15 name, mycube
character*1 digit(0:9)
data digit/'0','1',...,'9'/
:
do i = 1, NUMCUBES
cube(i) = "cube" // digit(i)
end do
call initcubecomm()
name = mycube()
:
if ((mynode() .eq. 0) .and.
cmpname(name, cube(1))) then
:
else
if (mynode() .eq. 1) then
if (name .eq. cube(1)) then
call crecv(NODETYPE,msgbuff,MAXMSGSIZE)
rcnt = infocount()
node = cubemap(cube(2),1)
call csend(INTERCUBE,msgbuff,rcnt,node,0)
call crecv(INTERCUBE,msgbuff,MAXMSGSIZE)
rcnt = infocount()
call csend(NODETYPE,msgbuff,rcnt,nextnode,0)
else
call crecv(INTERCUBE,msgbuff,MAXMSGSIZE)
rcnt = infocount()
call csend(NODETYPE,msgbuff,rcnt,nextnode,0)
call crecv(NODETYPE,msgbuff,MAXMSGSIZE)
rcnt = infocount()
node = cubemap(cube(1),1)
call csend(INTERCUBE,msgbuff,rcnt,node,0)
endif
else
call crecv(NODETYPE,msgbuff,MAXMSGSIZE)
rcnt = infocount()
call csend(NODETYPE,msgbuff,rcnt,nextnode,0)
endif
endif
endif
```